

The Influence of Empowerment Leadership on The Proactive Behavior of Employees in The Department of Women's Empowerment, Protection Children and Communities of Binjai City

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of empowerment leadership on proactive behavior in the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Services of Binjai City. This research was conducted using a causal associative quantitative approach. The sample used was all employees with a total of 61 people taken using proportional sampling. The research results show that empowering leadership has a positive and significant effect on proactive behavior. This is shown by the T-count value of T-count of $1.978 > t$ table 1.67109 , with a significance value of $0.053 < 0.05$. The regression coefficient shows that if empowerment leadership is increased by 1 unit, proactive behavior will increase by 0.059 units assuming other variables remain constant. Apart from that, the results of the determination test show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.046 or 4.60%, which indicates that empowerment leadership has a very low influence on proactive behavior, while the remaining 95.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. Thus, partially, empowering leadership has a positive but not significant effect on proactive behavior in the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service of Binjai City. This identifies that improvements in empowering leadership can contribute to increased proactive behavior.

Keywords: Empowerment leadership; Proactive behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Society play a crucial role in dealing with sensitive issues relating to women, children and society in general. However, in the context of the complexity of the duties and responsibilities carried out by the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service, challenges related to the effectiveness of employee performance may arise.

One factor that might influence employee performance is the leadership style applied in the organization. An empowering leadership style has the potential to increase employee motivation, involvement and creativity, which in turn can influence proactive behavior. However, in this context, goal orientation also has a significant role (Ahluwalia & Puji, 2020). Goal orientation, or clear and measurable goals, can be a strong motivator for employees in achieving desired results (Mohd. Syawal Prayogi et al., 2023).

Based on the explanation above, the real condition that occurs is the lack of implementation of an empowering leadership style in the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Services of Binjai City. Although this organization has a crucial role in dealing with sensitive issues related to women, children and society, the leadership style used effectively encourages employee motivation, involvement and creativity. This is caused by a lack of training or awareness about the importance of

empowerment in leading, as well as the existence of cultural or structural barriers within the organization that hinder the implementation of this leadership style.

According to (Covey, 2008) proactive behavior is more than just taking the initiative. Being proactive means taking responsibility for our own behavior (past, present, and future), and making choices based on principles and values rather than mood or circumstances. Proactive people are agents of change and choose not to be victims, not to be reactive, not to blame others.

To measure proactive behavior in this research, we refer to the indicators established by (Covey, 2008) as follows:

1. Freedom to choose a response that contains elements such as self-awareness, imagination, conscience and free will.
2. Taking initiative, which can be seen from two things, namely the ability to plan something immediately and anticipatory ability.

To realize proactive behavior, there are many factors that influence it. In this study, researchers limited themselves to empowering leadership factors mediated by goal orientation. Empowerment Leadership is "Super Leadership", which means individuals direct themselves. The terminology "Super Leadership" can also be called guided participation, where the leader helps his subordinates make their own decisions regarding their work (Amundsen & Martinsen, 2014)

Empowering leadership with its characteristics eliminates bureaucratic obstacles, helps subordinates find the meaning of work, gives subordinates the opportunity to make their own work decisions, can make subordinates feel involved and trusted in their abilities. This can increase subordinates' self-efficacy which helps them organize and carry out their work as well as possible (Ahluwalia & Puji, 2020).

According to (Amundsen & Martinsen, 2014) there are two dimensions, namely autonomy support and development support, leadership empowerment, which are described in indicators, namely:

- 1) Providing Autonomy in Decision Making
- 2) Acknowledging Individual Perspectives
- 3) Provide Clarification of Goals
- 4) Make Room for Mistakes
- 5) Providing Training and Learning
- 6) Provide Constructive Feedback
- 7) Encourage Career Growth
- 8) Assists in Personal Goal Setting

The aim of this research is to investigate and analyze the influence of empowerment leadership on the proactive behavior of employees at the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Services of Binjai City. It is hoped that this research can provide in-depth insight into the dynamics between leadership style and employee proactive behavior. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research with the aim of analyzing the pattern of relationships between variables with the aim of finding out the influence between two independent variables (exogenous) on the dependent variable (endogenous) (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). This research was carried out at the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service of Binjai City. This research was carried out from March to May 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population in this study is the entire number of employees in the Department of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Binjai City with a total of 61 employees with the following details:

Table 1. Population Details of the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and City Community Services

No.	Status	Number of people)
1.	ASN	23
2.	Honorary	28
3.	Task Force	10
Amount		61

Source: DP3AM Binjai City

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to (Sugiyono, 2019) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique if all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 61 employees.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

- Y = Proactive behavior
- X = Empowerment leadership
- a = Constant
- b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013). According to (Kuncooro, Munajad, 2013) the determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely empowering leadership (X), on the dependent variable, namely proactive behavior (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Empowerment leadership	61	3.00	5.00	4.1736	.46004
Proactive behavior	61	3.50	5.00	4.3607	.43904
Valid N (listwise)	61				

From the table above, it shows that the measurement results show that respondents rated empowering leadership and proactive behavior in the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Services of Binjai City as above average, with mean scores of 4,173 and 4,360 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is high, with almost the same standard deviation (0.4600 for Empowering leadership and 0.4390 for Proactive behavior), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have a fairly positive view of these two variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for the Empowerment Leadership Variable (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
X1	0.817 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X2	0.953 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X3	0.840 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X4	0.803 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X5	0.814 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X6	0.926 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X7	0.861 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
X8	0.868 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that the indicators for the Empowerment Leadership variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.2521 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05 so it can be concluded that the Empowerment Leadership variable indicators are valid (Sugiyono, 2017).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Proactive Behavior Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
Y.1	0.848 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid
Y.2	0.866 > 0.2521	0.000 < 0.050	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that all indicators in the proactive behavior variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.2521 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that the statements for the proactive behavior variable are valid (Sugiyono, 2016).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2016) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (a) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (a) value is > 0.61.

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Empowerment leadership	0.948	8
Proactive behavior	0.637	2

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (a) value of the empowering leadership and proactive behavior variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	6,737	1,009		6,677	,000
Empowerment leadership	,059	,030	,249	1,978	,053

Dependent Variable: Proactive behavior

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 6.737 + 0.059X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 6.737 means that if there is no empowering leadership, then there is proactive behavior of 6.737 points. The empowerment leadership regression coefficient is 0.311, meaning that empowerment leadership influences an increase in proactive behavior of 0.059 for every 1 point increase

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.249a	,062	,046	.85751

Predictors: (Constant), Empowering leadership

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.046 or 4.60%, which means that empowerment leadership has a very low influence on proactive behavior, while the remaining 95.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of empowerment leadership on proactive behavior in the Women's Empowerment, Child and Community Protection Department of Binjai City

Ha: There is an influence of empowerment leadership on proactive behavior in the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Services of Binjai City

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	6,737	1,009		6,677	,000
Empowerment leadership	,059	,030	,249	1,978	,053

Dependent Variable: Proactive behavior

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is $1.978 > t$ table 1.67109 , with a significance value of $0.053 < 0.05$, thus it can be stated that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted or there is a positive but not significant influence between empowerment leadership on proactive behavior in the Empowerment Service Women, Child Protection and the Community of Binjai City

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of empowering leadership on proactive behavior, these findings state that there is an influence of empowering leadership on proactive behavior, but it is not significant.

The implications of these findings emphasize the need to review empowerment leadership strategies in creating proactive behavior among employees. Although previous research shows a positive and significant relationship between empowering leadership and proactive behavior (Anwar Ul Haq et al., 2019), these findings highlight variations in its impact depending on the organizational context or other factors that may moderate it. The implication is that management needs to pay attention to the internal and external dynamics that influence the effectiveness of empowerment leadership, and adopt a more holistic approach in encouraging sustainable proactive behavior within the organization (Fatchurrohman et al., 2023). In addition, management needs to pay special attention to developing leadership skills that facilitate employee empowerment, such as open communication, providing constructive feedback, and appropriate division of authority, to create a work environment that promotes proactive and innovative behavior (Arafat et al., 2023)

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of the research data analysis and discussion described above, it can be concluded that:

1. The results of the hypothesis test show that empowering leadership has a positive but not very significant effect on proactive behavior. This can be seen from the T-count value of $1.978 > t$ table 1.67109 , with a significance value of $0.053 < 0.05$. This regression coefficient shows that if empowerment leadership is increased by 1 unit, then the change in proactive behavior as seen from the Y value will increase by 0.059 units assuming other variables are considered constant. Thus, partially empowering leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service of Binjai City
2. Based on the results of the termination test, it shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.046 or 4.60%, which means that empowerment leadership has a very low influence on proactive behavior, while the remaining 95.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

Suggestions

Based on the findings, discussion and conclusions of the research can be suggested to the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service as follows:

1. Institutions need to evaluate and review the empowerment leadership strategies currently implemented. Although empowering leadership does not have a significant effect on employee proactive behavior, a more holistic and multifaceted approach is needed to create a work environment that promotes proactive and innovative behavior. Management should focus on developing leadership skills that facilitate employee empowerment, such as open communication, providing constructive feedback, and appropriate distribution of authority.
2. Institutions need to provide sufficient support, autonomy and development opportunities to employees in order to increase the employee's own goal orientation. These empowering leadership practices will help employees be more focused and committed to achieving organizational goals. Therefore, institutions need to pay attention to leadership development that facilitates employee empowerment and creates a work environment that supports the creation of a clear and integrated goal orientation in an effort to achieve the organization's vision and mission.

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